

REPORT:

A2.3.1: Literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the liquid properties and microfluidic devices

Work package 2

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This report was written as part of activity 2.3.1 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

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1. Scope

This report addresses the activity A2.3.1 defined in the JRP protocol as:

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A2.3.1 M11	Using the liquid properties identified in A2.1.3, CMI, NQIS, IPQ, CETIAT and TUBITAK will perform a literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the liquid properties and microfluidic devices.	CMI , NQIS, IPQ, CETIAT, TUBITAK

In A2.1.3 the following liquid properties have been identified as the most relevant in microfluidic context:

- Density
- Viscosity
- Refractive index
- Contact angle with solid surfaces

This review is focused to standards related to the properties mentioned above and to specific measurement methods used in microfluidics. Outside the field of microfluidics, the measurement techniques for the properties mentioned above are well established and there are various standards related to them (hundreds in case of density and viscosity) for a myriad of applications. On the other hand, specific standards for microfluidics are missing, even if many measuring techniques in this field are emerging. Therefore, mostly we list general standards, which are not directly related to microfluidics. On top of that, we provide a literature review of microfluidic measurement techniques.

2. Density

2.1 Selected ISO standards

- ISO 3507:1999 Laboratory glassware — Pyknometers
- ISO 15212-1:1998 Oscillation-type density meters — Part 1: Laboratory instruments
- ISO 15212-2:2002 Oscillation-type density meters — Part 2: Process instruments for homogeneous liquids
- ISO 15212-2:2002 Technical Corrigendum 1 (2008) Oscillation-type density meters — Part 2: Process instruments for homogeneous liquids
- ISO 387:1977 Hydrometers — Principles of construction and adjustment
- ISO 649-1:1981 Laboratory glassware — Density hydrometers for general purposes — Part 1: Specification
- ISO 649-2:1981 Laboratory glassware — Density hydrometers for general purposes — Part 2: Test methods and use

- ISO 12185:1996 Crude petroleum and petroleum products — Determination of density — Oscillating U-tube method
- ISO 12185:1996 Technical Corrigendum 1 (2001) Crude petroleum and petroleum products — Determination of density — Oscillating U-tube method
- ISO 3838:2004 Crude petroleum and liquid or solid petroleum products — Determination of density or relative density — Capillary-stoppered pycnometer and graduated bicapillary pycnometer methods
- ISO 2811-1 Paints and varnishes — Determination of density — Part 1: Pycnometer method

2.2 Selected ASTM standards

- ASTM D3505-18 Standard Test Method for Density or Relative Density of Pure Liquid Chemicals
- ASTM D1475-13(2020) Standard Test Method for Density of Liquid Coatings, Inks, and Related Products
- ASTM D1217-20 Standard Test Method for Density and Relative Density (Specific Gravity) of Liquids by Bingham Pycnometer
- ASTM D4052-18a Standard Test Method for Density, Relative Density, and API Gravity of Liquids by Digital Density Meter
- ASTM D7042-21a Standard Test Method for Dynamic Viscosity and Density of Liquids by Stabinger Viscometer (and the Calculation of Kinematic Viscosity)
- ASTM D1481-17 Standard Test Method for Density and Relative Density (Specific Gravity) of Viscous Materials by Lipkin Bicapillary Pycnometer
- ASTM D7961-17 Standard Practice for Calibrating U-tube Density Cells over Large Ranges of Temperature and Pressure

2.3 Density measurement

2.3.1 Guides

- SIM Guidelines on the calibration of oscillation-type density meters; SIM MWG7/cg-02/v.00; 2016
- OIML G 14 Edition 2011, Density measurement

2.3.2 Measurement techniques

The density measurement techniques used in microfluidics are summarised in a recent paper [1]. The authors state:

For volumes around 1 ml, resonant based techniques, where change in the resonant frequency as a function of liquid density can be used, like vibrating glass tubes [2], surface acoustic waves [3, 4], tuning forks [5], quartz crystal microbalance [6] or thin film bulk acoustic waves [7]. For volumes around 1 μ l, again resonant based methods that use microtube resonators [8], microcantilever resonators immersed in liquid [9] or microtube resonators experiencing Coriolis force [10, 11] can be used. The vibrating signals are highly damped [12] if the sensor is immersed inside the liquid, significantly affecting the sensitivity [13]. However, by flowing liquid through the sensor, vibration damping can be significantly reduced and the sensitivity can be improved [14]. The energy dissipation in the vibrating structures typically is a function of viscosity, thus enabling to simultaneously obtain density and viscosity of a liquid by monitoring frequency shift and quality factor respectively.

References

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- [3] Martin S, Ricco A, Niemczyk T and Frye G, 1989, Characterization of SH acoustic plate mode liquid sensors, *Sensors Actuators* 20 253–68
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- [13] Ghatkesar M K, Rakhmatullina E, Lang H-P, Gerber C, Hegner M and Braun T, 2008, Multi-parameter microcantilever sensor for comprehensive characterization of newtonian fluids, *Sensors Actuators* 135 133–8
- [14] Burg T P and Manalis S R, 2003, Suspended microchannel resonators for biomolecular detection, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 83 2698–700

3. Viscosity

3.1 Selected ISO standards

- ISO/TR 3666:1998 Viscosity of water

- ISO 2884-1:1999 Paints and varnishes — Determination of viscosity using rotary viscometers — Part 1: Cone-and-plate viscometer operated at a high rate of shear
- ISO 2884-2:2003 Paints and varnishes — Determination of viscosity using rotary viscometers — Part 2: Disc or ball viscometer operated at a specified speed
- ISO/AWI 3104:2020 Petroleum products — Transparent and opaque liquids — Determination of kinematic viscosity and calculation of dynamic viscosity
- ISO 12058-1:2018 Plastics — Determination of viscosity using a falling-ball viscometer — Part 1: Inclined-tube method
- ISO 1628-1:2021 Plastics — Determination of the viscosity of polymers in dilute solution using capillary viscometers — Part 1: General principles
- ISO 3105:1994 Glass capillary kinematic viscometers — Specifications and operating instructions
- ISO 3219-2:2021 Rheology — Part 2: General principles of rotational and oscillatory rheometry
- ISO 3219-1:2021 Rheology — Part 1: Vocabulary and symbols for rotational and oscillatory rheometry
- ISO 2555:2018 Plastics — Resins in the liquid state or as emulsions or dispersions — Determination of apparent viscosity using a single cylinder type rotational viscometer method
- ISO 7884-2:1987 Glass — Viscosity and viscometric fixed points — Part 2: Determination of viscosity by rotation viscometers

3.2 Selected ASTM standards

- ASTM D7042-21a Standard Test Method for Dynamic Viscosity and Density of Liquids by Stabinger Viscometer (and the Calculation of Kinematic Viscosity)
- ASTM D7945-21a Standard Test Method for Determination of Dynamic Viscosity and Derived Kinematic Viscosity of Liquids by Constant Pressure Viscometer
- ASTM D445-21e1 Standard Test Method for Kinematic Viscosity of Transparent and Opaque Liquids (and Calculation of Dynamic Viscosity)
- ASTM D446-12(2017) Standard Specifications and Operating Instructions for Glass Capillary Kinematic Viscometers
- ASTM D8092-17 Standard Test Method for Field Determination of Kinematic Viscosity Using a Microchannel Viscometer

- ASTM D1545-13(2017) Standard Test Method for Viscosity of Transparent Liquids by Bubble Time Method
- ASTM D5478-13(2018) Standard Test Methods for Viscosity of Materials by a Falling Needle Viscometer
- ASTM E3116-18 Standard Test Method for Viscosity Measurement Validation of Rotational Viscometers
- ASTM D2196-20 Standard Test Methods for Rheological Properties of Non-Newtonian Materials by Rotational Viscometer
- ASTM E2975-16e1 Standard Test Method for Calibration or Calibration Verification of Concentric Cylinder Rotational Viscometers
- ASTM D5125-10(2020)e1 Standard Test Method for Viscosity of Paints and Related Materials by ISO Flow Cups
- ASTM D1200-10(2018) Standard Test Method for Viscosity by Ford Viscosity Cup
- ASTM D4212-16 Standard Test Method for Viscosity by Dip-Type Viscosity Cups

3.2 Viscosity measurement in microfluidics

There are two recent reviews on this topic – a review of microfluidic viscometers for biochemical and biomedical applications [15] and a review of microfluidic devices for rheological characterisation [16]. The tables 1-5 below summarising the viscosity measurement methods in microfluidics are taken from the reference [15]. For references regarding the specific methods in the tables see [15].

References

- [15] S B Puneeth, M B Kulkarni and S Goel, 2021, Microfluidic viscometers for biochemical and biomedical applications: A review, *Eng. Res. Express* **3**, 022003, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2631-8695/abfd47>
- [16] Del Giudice F, 2022, Review of Microfluidic Devices for Rheological Characterisation, *Micromachines* **13**, 167; <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi13020167>

Table 1. Summary of Electro-mechanical based microviscometers.

Fabrication technique	Sample volume	Range	Error margin	Application and advantages	Drawbacks
Silicon Cantilever	NA-	20–30000 mPa.s	-NA-	It is used as a rheometer.	The cumbersome fabrication process, and not a POC device.
Piezoelectric (PZT) cantilever	-NA-	60–270 mPa.s	-NA-	Thin film viscosity.	
An array of piezo cantilever	~2.4 μ l	~1–30 mPa.s	< 10%	Demonstrated with water and 33% of glycerol for viscosity measurement.	Difficult to align the cantilever position, Challenges in the calibration of the device, placing of fluid on the exact region of a cantilever.
Electrical impedance of piezoelectric cantilever	-NA-	10 to 2000 mPa.s	~8%	Executed using olive and silicon oil for determining the viscosity.	Fabrication is a challenging process, an issue in the accuracy of the impedance measurement.
Ionic polymer-metal composite (IPMC) bimetallic strip	-NA-	-NA-	-NA-	Used as a proof-of-concept and viscosity of sucrose solutions was measured.	Non-microfluidic platform
Cantilever with piezo	-NA-	~10 mPa.s	-NA-	Used with various chemical fluids for the determination of viscosity.	Non-microfluidic platform
Piezo resonated in flexural and in torsional mode	-NA-	200 μ Pa.s – 1000 μ Pa.s	-NA-	Condition monitoring involving fluid media.	The error margin is more than the substantial range, analyzed from the result tabulated in the manuscript.
Wire resonated at low frequency	-NA-	0.2 mPa.s – 200 mPa.s	-NA-	To calculate the viscous level of DI water and glycerol mixture.	Non-microfluidic platform
Tuning fork dipped in the fluid whose viscosity needs to be measured	-NA-	0.2 mPa.s – 20 mPa.s	~1%	-NA-	For each test, an airtight environment needs to be established.
Micro machining	~13 nl	<5 mPa.s	-NA-	-NA-	Achieving 100% of several microchannels in fabrication is challenging
3D Printer based microchannel	~200 μ l	< 10 mPa.s	~6%	To measure the viscosity of biochemical fluids	Non-conducting fluids cannot be used for measuring the viscosity

Table 2. Summary of Optical based microviscometers.

Fabrication technique	Sample Volume	Range	Error margin	Applications	Drawbacks
Optical fiber-based forward scattering in fluid	-NA-	0.3 mPa.s – 2 mPa.s	-NA-	Glycerol- DI water wt% were measured	Non- microfluidic
Fluid filled in optical tweezer	-NA-	< 10 mPa.s	-NA-	-NA-	Complicated setup even for laboratory
SLA 3D Printer based Y-microchannel	Few 100 μ l	< 50 mPa.s	-NA-	Bio-diesel blending, milk adulteration detection	Microscope dependent
PDMS based microchannel cantilever	Few 100 μ l	< 50 mPa.s	-NA-	Blood viscosity measurement for haematocrit variations	Fabrication is a challenge, impedance measurement accuracy
An optical laser used to know the frequency of the cantilevers dipped in fluid	100 μ l	0.6–2 mPa.s	<6%	The viscosity of biochemical fluids was measured.	The variation in the laser height leads to error. The device design is for a very low range.
Etched optical fiber placed in an angle	0.5–4 ml	<1000 mPa.s	-NA-	Various concentration of glycerol solutions	Completed setup with inclined optic fiber
Ostwald viscometer with webcam	11 ml	-NA-	0.04%		Glass capillary need to handled carefully, need the density of the fluid to calculate the viscosity

Table 3. Summary of Paper-based microviscometers and μ PADs.

Fabrication technique	Sample Volume	Range	Error margin	Applications	Drawbacks
Wax Printing on Whatman paper	~50 μ l	0.5–10 mPa.s	<6%	Measurement of viscosity for milk, biofluids	Not compatible with oil and petroleum products
	< 20 μ l	0.5–10 mPa.s	<8%	Measurement of human fluids such as bovine serum albumin (BSA), Lysozyme, Human saliva	
PCL filament 3DP on Whatman paper	~50 μ l	0.5–10 mPa.s	<8%		Semi- Automated microwevice

Table 4. Summary of Droplet-based microfluidic viscometers.

Fabrication technique	Sample Volume	Range	Error margin	Applications	Drawbacks
Aluminum (Al) mold	~20 μ l	NA	<11.2%	Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids	Sensitivity of device depends on micropillar arrangement
Standard 100-mm Borofloat wafers	340 μ l	NA	NA	Measurement of Blood coagulation	Used for clinical method of thromboelastography
Softlithography	10 μ l	2-80 mPa.s	<2%	Measurement of silicone oil	Pressure driven flow
Polymethyl-methacrylate (PMMA)	NA	4-334 mPa.s	NA	Viscosities in tubular systems is essential for industries transporting fluid media	50 cm plastic pipe diameter filled with liquid

Table 5. Summary of Integrated microfluidic viscometers.

Fabrication technique	Sample Volume	Range	Error margin	Applications	Drawbacks
Softlithography	<400 μ l	NA	NA	Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids	Pressure sensor based on electrofluidic circuits
PDMS and Tygon tube	NA	4.1 kPa -214.3 kPa	13.7 %	Measurement of Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids	Required external pump for fluid management
Softlithography and Deep reactive-ion etching	25 μ l	NA	\pm 5%	Measurement of Blood	Brookfield viscometer based operation
Polymeric materials	<50 μ l	3×10^{-3} - 4×10^{-2} Pa.s	<0.1%	Blood and saliva	Newtonian fluids cannot be measured

4. Refractive index

4.1 Selected ISO, ASTM and OIML standards

- ISO 5661:1983 Petroleum products — Hydrocarbon liquids — Determination of refractive index
- ISO 1739:1975 Butter — Determination of the refractive index of the fat (Reference method)
- ISO 21395-1:2020 Optics and photonics — Test method for refractive index of optical glasses — Part 1: Minimum deviation method
- ISO 21395-2:2022 Optics and photonics — Test method for refractive index of optical glasses — Part 2: V-block refractometer method
- ISO 489:2022 Plastics — Determination of refractive index
- ASTM D1747-09(2019) Standard Test Method for Refractive Index of Viscous Materials
- ASTM D1218-21 Standard Test Method for Refractive Index and Refractive Dispersion of Hydrocarbon Liquids
- ASTM E1303-95(2017) Standard Practice for Refractive Index Detectors Used in Liquid Chromatography
- OIML R142:2008 Automated refractometers: Methods and means of verification

4.2 Refractive index measurement in microfluidics

Introduction of a recent paper [17] contains an overview of refractive index measurement methods in microfluidics including the corresponding references. The methods are summarised in the table below. The references for the specific methods in the table can be found in [17].

References

- [17] F. Purr, M. Bassu, R. D. Lowe, B. Thürmann, A. Dietzel and T. P. Burg, 2017, Asymmetric nanofluidic grating detector for differential refractive index measurement and biosensing, *Lab Chip* **17**, 4265, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7lc00929a>

Table 1 Microfluidic refractive index measurement methods

Technology	Detection limit	Background cancelation/self-referencing	Size/volume	Ref.
Surface plasmon resonance	1×10^{-7} – 2×10^{-5} RIU	No	20–150 μ L (ref. 24)	24, 25
Young interferometer	1.8×10^{-8} RIU (ref. 26)	Yes, reference arm	6 μ L (ref. 26)	26–29
Microinterferometric backscatter detector	6.9×10^{-9} RIU	Yes, two capillaries: fringe subtraction	50 nL	30
Ring resonator	3.16×10^{-6} RIU (ref. 31) 3.8×10^{-8} RIU (ref. 32) 5.0×10^{-6} RIU (ref. 33)	Independent reference structures: multiple sensors on one chip with beam splitter ³³ yes, double resonator ³⁴	200 \times 20 μ m/10 μ L min ⁻¹ (ref. 33) resonator cross section: 68 μ m (ref. 32)	31–34
Fiber Bragg grating	2.2×10^{-5} RIU	No	3.45 μ m per hole	35, 36
Fabry-Perot cavity	1.7×10^{-5} RIU (ref. 37)	No	Cavity width = 24.5 μ m (ref. 37)	37–43
Photonic crystal: nanoscaled optofluidic sensor array (NOSA)	7×10^{-5} RIU	Independent reference structures: multiple sensor structures on one chip with one waveguide	Hole diameter 200 nm, 250 nm deep, 8 holes per sensor	44
Diffraction grating	1.9×10^{-6} RIU (ref. 45 and 46) 6×10^{-7} RIU (ref. 47)	I0 as reference	50 μ m thick fluid layer ⁴⁷	45–47
Micro edge	3×10^{-3} RIU	No	20 μ m deep; 250 μ m wide	48
μ -Image defocusing 3-pinhole aperture	53.7 pixel per RIU	Self-calibration: reference fluids included on chip – one image measurement	50 μ m wide; 17–82 μ m deep	49
Tapered fiber	1.42×10^{-5} RIU (ref. 50)	No	Diameter of fiber 200 μ m; 6 mm long ⁹	9, 50

5. Contact angle

5.1 Selected ISO standards

- ISO 15989:2004 Plastics — Film and sheeting — Measurement of water-contact angle of corona-treated films
- ISO/TS 14778:2021 Paper and board — Measurement of water contact angle by optical methods
- ISO 19403-1:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 1: Terminology and general principles
- ISO 19403-2:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 2: Determination of the surface free energy of solid surfaces by measuring the contact angle
- ISO 19403-3:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 3: Determination of the surface tension of liquids using the pendant drop method
- ISO 19403-4:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 4: Determination of the polar and dispersive fractions of the surface tension of liquids from an interfacial tension
- ISO 19403-5:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 5: Determination of the polar and dispersive fractions of the surface tension of liquids from contact angles measurements on a solid with only a disperse contribution to its surface energy
- ISO 19403-6:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 6: Measurement of dynamic contact angle
- ISO 19403-7:2017 Paints and varnishes — Wettability — Part 7: Measurement of the contact angle on a tilt stage (roll-off angle)

5.2 Selected ASTM standards

- ASTM C813-20 Standard Test Method for Hydrophobic Contamination on Glass by Contact Angle Measurement
- ASTM D5946-17 Standard Test Method for Corona-Treated Polymer Films Using Water Contact Angle Measurements
- ASTM D7334-08(2022) Standard Practice for Surface Wettability of Coatings, Substrates and Pigments by Advancing Contact Angle Measurement
- ASTM D7490-13(2022) Standard Test Method for Measurement of the Surface Tension of Solid Coatings, Substrates and Pigments using Contact Angle Measurements

5.3 Guidelines and protocols on contact angle measurement

- T. Huhtamäki, X. Tian, J. T. Korhonen and R. H. A. Ras, 2018, Surface-wetting characterization using contact-angle measurements, *Nature Protocols* **13**, 1521–1538, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-018-0003-z>
- J. Drelich, 2013, Guidelines to measurements of reproducible contact angles using a sessile-drop technique, *Surf. Innov.* **1**, 248–254, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1680/si.13.00010>

5.4 Review papers on contact angle measurement

- R. Akbari, C. Antonini, 2021, Contact angle measurements: From existing methods to an open-source tool, *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **294**, 102470, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2021.102470>
- J. W. Drelich, 2019, Contact angles: From past mistakes to new developments through liquid-solid adhesion measurements, *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* **267**, 1–14, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2019.02.002>
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